

COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF CEPSTRUM-BASED ANALYSIS AND MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS FOR AXIAL COMPRESSOR DAMAGE ASSESSMENT

Mario Eck*
Dieter Peitsch

Chair of Aero Engines
Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics
Technische Universität Berlin
Marchstr. 12-14
10587 Berlin, Germany
Email: mario.eck@tu-berlin.de
Email: dieter.peitsch@tu-berlin.de

Jan Mihalyovics

Siemens Energy Global GmbH & Co. KG
Huttenstrasse 12
10553 Berlin, Germany
Email: jan.mihalyovics@siemens-energy.com

ABSTRACT

Early detection of compressor damage in gas turbines reduces downtime and unplanned maintenance but is hindered by scarce labeled fault data. Two axial-compressor damage-detection approaches are compared: a cepstrum-based Compressor Damage Index (CDI) and supervised machine-learning classifiers. Experiments employ a single-stage axial-compressor rig at Technische Universität Berlin with stereolithographic 3D-printed blades. Controlled damage states—breakouts, twisted blades, bent blades, and fouling—are implemented. An artificial pressure-signal generator synthesizes dynamic pressure time series conditioned on damage type to expand training data. The CDI processes dynamic-pressure measurements through preprocessing and cepstrum analysis to yield a scalar anomaly index. Machine-learning models are trained on synthetic signals to predict damage presence and class, then evaluated on measured signals from the rig. Both approaches separate baseline from damaged operation and discriminate among the tested classes on experimental data; the CDI yields interpretable indicators, and the classifiers deliver multiclass decisions with synthetic-to-real transfer. The measured pressure time series for baseline and damaged cases are publicly released. A validated workflow that couples physics-informed signal processing, synthetic data generation, and classification supports compressor health monitoring.

Keywords: axial compressor health monitoring, damage

detection, deep learning, cepstrum-based analysis

NOMENCLATURE

Roman

$x[n]$	discrete-time dynamic pressure signal
n	time-sample index
N	frame length (samples)
$w[n]$	analysis window applied to each frame
$X[k]$	DFT of $w[n]x[n]$ (complex spectrum)
$ X[k] $	single-sided magnitude spectrum at bin k
k	index (frequency-bin index in $X[k]$; rahmonic order in τ_k)
m	quefrency-sample index
$C_r[m]$	real cepstrum sample at index m
$C_r(\tau)$	real cepstrum as a function of quefrency τ
f_s	sampling frequency
f_r	shaft (rotor) frequency
K	number of rahmonic windows aggregated
W_k	quefrency window around τ_k
CDI	Compressor Damage Index (frame-wise scalar)
z	standardized deviation of CDI (z -score)

Greek

α	quefrency (seconds), $\tau = m/f_s$
τ	quefrency (seconds), $\tau = m/f_s$
τ_k	expected rahmonic quefrency, $\tau_k \approx k/f_r$
$\Delta\tau$	half-width of the rahmonic window W_k

*Address all correspondence to this author.

μ_0	baseline mean of CDI (healthy data)
σ_0	baseline standard deviation of CDI
$\Delta\%$	relative change of CDI in percent
Δ_f	uniform spectral spacing

Operators / Special Accents and Subscripts

$\mathcal{F}\{\cdot\}$	discrete Fourier transform (DFT)
$\mathcal{F}^{-1}\{\cdot\}$	inverse discrete Fourier transform (IDFT)
$\log(\cdot)$	logarithm applied elementwise
$ \cdot $	magnitude
$(\cdot)_0$	baseline (healthy) quantity

Abbreviations

BPF	Blade-Passing Frequency
CDI	Compressor Damage Index
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DFT	Discrete Fourier Transform
DP / NS	Design Point / Near Stall
EMA	Exponential Moving Average
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio

1 INTRODUCTION

Axial-compressor health directly affects efficiency and safety, making reliable damage detection essential. The effectiveness of cepstrum-based techniques and machine-learning models for identifying damaged operation is assessed alongside a concise review of established diagnostics. Pfeifer and Brummel [1] describe a diagnostic pipeline that transforms time-domain dynamic-pressure measurements to discrete spectra via FFT, aggregates spectra spatially and temporally into a virtual spectrum, computes cepstra, and forms speed-synchronous cepstral intervals whose aggregated value is compared against a target derived from healthy operation. Dynamic pressure sensors are placed at critical locations to ensure coverage, and the target/actual comparison is designed to be robust to operating and environmental variation, enabling timely indications of deviation from nominal behavior [1]. Unsteady wall-pressure-based diagnostics have demonstrated sensitivity to minor blade faults under realistic conditions. Mathioudakis et al. [2] validated spectral features and derived indices on a commercial gas turbine, showing that unsteady pressure signals permit fault identification independent of operating point. Loukis et al. [3] advanced automated fault recognition by extracting discriminants from spectral patterns for real-time, operator-independent diagnosis with high success rates. Complementary sensing expands coverage: Loukis et al. [4] combined acoustic emission, casing vibration, shaft displacement, and unsteady inner-wall pressure, demonstrating that specific measurements are preferentially sensitive to particular

defect types and that their integration increases diagnostic accuracy. Data-driven prediction further improves decision support. Taylor et al. [5] coupled rapid experimental testing with physically parameterized features to train machine-learning models on damaged-blade configurations; using 100 of 125 cases, the method predicted compressor operability with $\approx 2\%$ accuracy at 95% confidence and yielded interpretable physical insights into damaged-compressor behavior. Risk-informed interpretation benefits from structured assessment. Aust and Pons [6] proposed a three-dimensional framework for visual inspection that augments criticality and severity with a contextual cofactor to reflect detectability, enabling clear go/no-go decisions through a 3D risk matrix and expert validation. The defect taxonomy introduced by Aust and Pons [7] provides a consistent scheme for categorizing blade conditions used herein; only a subset of defects from these publications is considered [6, 7].

2 METHODOLOGY

This section describes the comprehensive methodology employed in this study, including the experimental setup, which not only serves to study certain blade damages but also provides the foundation for generating experimental validation data. To expand the available dataset, we subsequently describe the data augmentation strategy developed on the basis of the experimentally obtained signals. Building on these synthetic data resources, we introduce two complementary methodological approaches: a cepstrum-based analysis and an deep learning-driven framework.

Experimental Setup

This section details the experimental single-stage axial compressor rig at Technische Universität Berlin. The experimental investigation was conducted using the CATAO (Compressor Aerodynamics Tangible and Application Oriented) one-stage axial compressor rig at Technische Universität Berlin. The CATAO facility is designed for practice-oriented research and education in compressor aerodynamics. A schematic representation of the compressor rig is shown in Figure 1. The compressor stage comprises Variable Inlet Guide Vanes (VIGVs), a rotor and a stator, with geometric and operational parameters summarized in Table 1. A throttle installed at the outlet allows the operating point to be adjusted by varying the mass flow rate. The rotor blades are designed using classic analytical methods, incorporating various design techniques such as direct profile designs and blade optimization approaches using sweep and lean. The blades are manufactured using rapid prototyping techniques with stereolithographic (SLA) 3D printers, enabling the production of an entire compressor stage within a very short timeframe. The rotor disk features a circumferential groove that enables individual rotor blades or even an entire rotor set to be changed quickly. Rotor

TABLE 1. CATAO Compressor Stage Specifications

Casing diameter	450 mm
Rotor hub-to-tip ratio	0.8
Rotor tip clearance (datum)	0.5 mm (1.25% chord)
Rotor speed	2,940 rpm
Rel. Mach number	0.22
Chord-based Reynolds number	1.7×10^5
Blade count (R/S)	51/48
Design flow coefficient	0.4
Design total-to-static pressure rise	0.5
Design mass flow	2.15 kg/s
Design total pressure ratio	1.017

tip clearance is set to 1.25% of the tip blade chord length. The downstream stator, which is likewise installed in casing segments with a circumferential groove, is a cantilevered stator.

FIGURE 1. Axial compressor stage

Dynamic pressure was measured with flush-mounted piezoresistive transducers (Kulite XCQ-062) in the casing at the rotor leading-edge tip region. Signals were conditioned (DEWETRON DAQP-STG) and digitized with 24-bit modules (DEWETRON ORION-1624-200) using the instrument's internal bridge conditioning. All sensors were calibrated in-house against a pressure standard prior to testing. Rig geometry and

operating parameters are summarized in Fig. 1 and Table 1.

Failure Cases Studied

In this research, we have designed and implemented a series of controlled failure scenarios on our experimental test rig. We selected these failure cases to represent common and critical types of damage that can occur in axial compressors. We initially presented the taxonomy used for these failure cases in [7]. By introducing specific faults and measuring the compressor's response, we aim to assess the sensitivity and reliability of our detection methods across a range of damage types and severities. We assign a unique identifier to each failure case using a notation such as e.g. (BO10), which we will consistently use throughout this paper in text, figures, and graphs to facilitate clear and unambiguous reference. The failure cases studied are as follows:

(BO50) 50% Breaking

In this failure case, we simulate severe blade damage characterized by a symmetrical breakage at the leading edge (LE) of a single blade, starting from the blade tip, extending to 50% of the chord length. This represents a complete separation of the blade into two or more large-sized pieces due to external forces or internal stresses. Different defects, such as cracks, nicks, dents, and notches, often precede this failure and, in combination with causes like impact, fatigue, or operational stresses, lead to material separation and a broken engine blade. This type of damage is also referred to as *burst*, *breakage*, *break-off*, *broken*, *cut*, *fracture*, *liberation*, or *rupture*. See Figure 2.

(BO30) 30% Breaking

Similar to (BO50), this case involves a breakage starting at 30% of the chord length, extending from the blade tip, representing moderate damage.

(BO10) 10% Breaking

This case features a breakage beginning at 10% of the chord length, extending from the blade tip, simulating minor damage.

(TW) Twist

In this failure case, we simulate a blade deformation also known as *curl*, characterized by a rounded fold in the rotating blade after contact with a fixed, non-moving part, such as the engine casing. This defect, also referred to as *warped*, can occur when the blade tip rubs against the engine case—a phenomenon known as a *tip rub*. Potential causes of such tip rubs include elongation or creep of the blade, which can result from heavy landings or overloading. Other sources include deposits on the casing, compressor surge, or missed maintenance inspections and incorrect procedures during maintenance of tip clearance. To replicate this deformation, we twist a blade linearly from 0 degrees at the root to 8 degrees at the tip, against the rotor rotation direction. See Figure 2.

FIGURE 2. Damage parameterization: breakage, twist and bent

FIGURE 3. Compressor characteristic: Speed lines with different damage types - two damaged blades installed opposite each other

BE Bent

In this failure case, we bend a section of the leading edge of a single blade, resulting in an angular change from the original shape or contour, usually caused by a lateral force. Specifically, starting from 50% of the chord length, the leading edge is shifted in the circumferential direction, and the deformation follows a circular arc in the radial direction. This deformation affects approximately one third to one quarter of the blade span. We also refer to this type of deformation as *creased*, *distorted*, *folded*, *kinked*, or *leaning*. A lateral impact, such as from Foreign Object Damage (FOD) or Domestic Object Damage (DOD), can cause this deformation. See Figure 2.

To provide an initial indication of how each damage type influences compressor performance, two damaged blades were installed opposite each other and transient speed lines were recorded (Figure 3). Even with only two blades affected, a measurable impact on performance was observed. This effect is most pronounced in the 50% breakage case, which reduces the stall margin the most. In contrast, bent blades show the smallest impact on overall compressor performance.

Data Generation - Data Augmentation

This section outlines the procedure for experimentally acquiring data that capture the unique damage signature associated with each type of blade damage. These experimentally derived signatures form the basis for the generation of synthetic datasets, where the original measurements are incorporated and extended to represent a wide range of damage configurations and scenarios.

At first, two rotor blades with the same damage type were installed in the compressor rig and measurements were performed. The pressures recorded by the over-tip sensors were ensemble-averaged phase-locked to a single rotor revolution to obtain a representative signal including the blade passing signature of 51 rotor blades. The pure damage signature was extracted by subtracting the ensemble average of the reference (undamaged) configuration from the ensemble average of the damaged configuration. This process was repeated for each type of damage and for each investigated operating point (design point - DP / near stall - NS) to create individual damage signatures. The latter includes three passages to show the impact of the damage on the neighboring blades. Figure 4 presents damage signatures under different operating conditions, with the left side depicting design conditions and the right side illustrating near-stall conditions. Each plot contains three rotor passages, capturing the periodic nature of the pressure fluctuations. The effects of blade damage on the aerodynamic loading of neighboring blades are clearly visible, as the damage not only influences the affected blade but also alters the surrounding flow field.

Each damage class exhibits distinct signatures characterized by an amplitude burst which in some cases exceeds 100% of the initial blade passing signature fluctuation. In general, these signatures become more pronounced when blade loading increases, as seen in the near-stall condition. While a twisted blade does not appear to noticeably affect its neighboring blade, all other damage cases do. In addition, whereas the twist primarily increases the peak suction of the affected blade itself, the other damage types lead to an increase in pressure amplitude, most prominently around mid-pitch near the suction side.

Data augmentation was carried out using two complementary approaches. In the first approach, synthetic datasets were generated by superimposing the extracted damage signatures onto the experimentally obtained reference signal (undamaged rotor), which were subsequently employed for network training and validation. In the second approach, a signal generator was used to produce harmonic signals representing artificial blade passing signatures, which were then overlaid with the experimentally obtained damage signatures. Both augmentation strategies were applied to support the validation of the neural network-based framework as well as the Compressor Damage Index (CDI) approach. The artificial pressure signal genera-

FIGURE 4. Damage signatures for design conditions (DP) and near stall (NS) - damaged blade located at position 0

tor synthesizes rotor-synchronous pressure traces by modulating a sinusoidal carrier with a second sinusoid to emulate blade-passing dynamics. Key parameters - sampling rate, blade count, rotational speed, and amplitude - are user-settable to reproduce different machines and operating points. Structured revolution-synchronous noise and broadband stochastic noise can be superimposed to reflect periodic disturbances and sensor/operational variability. Experimentally obtained damage signatures (e.g., missing or twisted blades, edge breakouts) are injectible to study fault effects and mixtures. Signal validity is checked against empirical data using frequency-domain analysis (FFT) and real-cepstrum inspection to confirm expected spectral lines and cepstral rahmonics. The generator also supports step-like fault onsets during a run to assess detection latency. An interactive interface with widgets exposes parameters and immediate visual feedback. Generated signals can be exported in various formats for subsequent analysis and machine-learning workflows.

3 CEPSTRUM BASED DAMAGE DETECTION

This section introduces a cepstrum-based framework for detecting compressor damage from dynamic-pressure measure-

ments. Section 3.1 defines the Compressor Damage Index (CDI) as a scalar metric derived from the *real-cepstrum* by aggregating cepstral energy within speed-synchronous quefrequency windows (“rahmonics”), linking rotation-induced spectral periodicities to an interpretable indicator. Section 3.2 details the processing workflow - short-time FFT, real-cepstrum computation, rahmonic identification, CDI formation, and comparison against a healthy baseline - to quantify deviations from nominal compressor operation.

Compressor Damage Index Development

Real-cepstrum analysis underpins the CDI by converting periodic spacing in the magnitude spectrum into impulses in the quefrequency domain. For a discrete-time signal $x[n]$ (sampling frequency f_s) with DFT $X[k]$,

$$C_r[m] = \mathcal{F}^{-1}\{\log|X[k]|\}, \quad \tau = \frac{m}{f_s}. \quad (1)$$

where τ (s) denotes quefrequency. A spectral line pattern with uniform spacing Δf produces a cepstral peak at $\tau \approx 1/\Delta f$; harmonically related spacings yield a sequence of “rahmonic” peaks [8, 9]. The logarithmic magnitude reduces spectral tilt and converts multiplicative transfer effects into additive terms, rendering these peaks robust to smooth transmission variations.

In axial compressors, blade-row interactions and flow nonuniformities impose amplitude modulation on dynamic pressure, generating sideband combs around rotor shaft-speed and blade-passing components. Structural or aerodynamic damage perturbs these modulations and, consequently, the cepstral pattern (peak locations and amplitudes). The CDI leverages this mapping by aggregating cepstral energy within selected quefrequency windows W_k centered at $\tau_k \approx k/f_r$ for $k = 1, \dots, K$ and contrasts the result with a healthy baseline to quantify deviation. This construction links physically interpretable spectral periodicities to a scalar damage indicator suitable for condition monitoring [1].

Signal Processing and Rahmonic Analysis

Dynamic pressure measurements are analyzed by a short-time FFT and real-cepstrum processing to expose rotation-induced spectral periodicities and compute the CDI.

Pipeline

1. **Framing and FFT:** The time series $x[n]$ is segmented into N -sample frames with window $w[n]$ (optional overlap). The single-sided magnitude spectrum is $|X[k]| = |\mathcal{F}\{w[n]x[n]\}|$.
2. **Real-cepstrum:** The real-cepstrum converts uniformly spaced spectral lines into impulses in the quefrequency domain:

$$C_r[m] = \mathcal{F}^{-1}\{\log|X[k]|\}, \quad \tau = \frac{m}{f_s}. \quad (2)$$

3. **Rahmonic identification:** For shaft frequency f_r , the expected quefrequency peaks (“rahmonics”) occur at $\tau_k \approx \frac{k}{f_r}$, $k = 1, \dots, K$. Local maxima of $C_r(\tau)$ are detected within windows $W_k = [\tau_k - \Delta\tau, \tau_k + \Delta\tau]$.
4. **CDI per frame:** Cepstral energy around the first K rahmonics is aggregated to form a scalar index

$$\text{CDI} = \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{\tau \in W_k} |C_r(\tau)|. \quad (3)$$

Speed-synchronous analysis is enforced by updating τ_k with the measured f_r for each frame.

5. **Baseline and deviation:** A baseline μ_0 and σ_0 is estimated from confirmed healthy operation. Frame-wise deviation is quantified by $z = \frac{\text{CDI} - \mu_0}{\sigma_0}$ (or by the relative change $\Delta\% = 100(\text{CDI} - \mu_0)/\mu_0$). Aggregation over time (e.g., median of recent frames) yields a robust trend.

Interpretation Elevated energy in W_k relative to baseline indicates strengthened amplitude modulation of blade-passing components and thus a deviation from nominal compressor behavior. The magnitude of z reflects severity; the pattern across k aids fault discrimination. Stable, low z values indicate consistency with the compressors baseline.

Operationalization. CDI is computed framewise on 8 s pressure records ($f_s=250\text{kHz}$) using Blackman windows ($N=2^{15}$, no overlap). The real cepstrum uses the base-10 log magnitude spectrum with zero-padding for interpolation. Rahmonic windows are centered at $\tau_k=k/f_r$ with $f_r=2940/60\text{Hz}$, using $K=6$ rahmonics and ± 3 side-bins per rahmonic. The baseline CDI_0 is the mean over the pre-onset interval (first 2 s). We report the percent change $\Delta\% = 100(\text{CDI}_t - \text{CDI}_0)/\text{CDI}_0$ and its EMA (smoothing factor $\alpha_{EMA}=0.5$, decision trace starts at frame 3); both traces are shown in Fig. 14. All metrics use the same events as the CNN, enabling a direct $\text{CDI} \leftrightarrow \text{CNN}$ comparison.

4 DEEP LEARNING BASED DAMAGE CLASSIFICATION

The present study employs a convolutional neural network (CNN) for classifying the specific damage type of compressor blades. What makes this approach unique is the use of synthetically generated data for network training, while the final validation is conducted with experimental data recorded at real damage scenarios. This section is organized into four main parts: the generation of training datasets, the development and optimization of the 1D CNN architecture, network training and the successive steps of model validation.

FIGURE 5. Data augmentation: synthetic signal generation at DP conditions, top: original signal including two blades of damage class “bent”, bottom: synthetic signal including five blades of the same damage class randomly distributed

Data generation

Synthetic damage signals were generated by adding the damage signatures to the experimentally obtained reference blade signature. The superposition was applied at up to 15 circumferential blade positions randomly distributed around the annulus, with the condition that at least two damaged blades were positioned adjacent to each other. Each training signal has a length equivalent to a single rotor revolution. Data from breakout damage types ranging between 10% and 50% were labeled under a single class, “breakout”, for network training. The model was therefore not tasked with distinguishing between different severities but instead with learning the variability in their appearance. For each class and each operating point (DP/NS), 240 sequences were generated, resulting in a total of 1200 data sets, 80% of which were used for training and the remaining 20% for validation.

As an example, Figure 5 presents a comparison between the original phase-averaged signal obtained from the experiments and the reconstructed signal for the bent blade damage case. The top section of the figure displays the original signal, where two bent blades have been installed opposite each other. In contrast, the bottom section illustrates the reconstructed signal, which incorporates five randomly distributed bent blades.

Model Development and Optimization

The 1D convolutional neural network (CNN) developed in this study was designed for a multi-classification task. Each input sample is being represented by a pressure sequence consisting of 5100 data points, covering a complete rotor revolution. The network architecture was structured to progressively extract increasingly complex features from these one-dimensional sig-

FIGURE 6. Classifier: 1D-CNN - FNN

nals (Figure 6). It begins with a sequence input layer, followed by three convolutional blocks composed of convolutional layers with ReLU activations, batch normalization, and max-pooling operations in the first two blocks. The number of convolutional filters in each block was scaled according to an optimized parameter, allowing the network to adapt its representational capacity to the complexity of the classification task. After the convolutional stages, a global average pooling layer was introduced to condense feature maps into compact representations, thereby reducing the number of trainable parameters and mitigating overfitting. This was followed by two fully connected layers, whose sizes were likewise determined by optimized parameters, with a dropout layer in between to enhance generalization. The network concluded with a softmax output layer, providing class probabilities for the four conditions under investigation: undamaged blade, breakout, blade curl and bent blades.

To ensure optimal performance, a Bayesian optimization framework was employed to determine the best combination of architectural design and training hyperparameters (Figure 7). This approach was selected over traditional grid or random search methods because it allows for efficient navigation of high-dimensional and computationally expensive search spaces, which are typical in deep learning tasks. The optimization process simultaneously tuned the initial learning rate, L2 regularization strength, dropout rate, mini-batch size, and scaling parameters controlling the number of convolutional filters "F" and fully connected nodes "N". For each candidate configuration, a network was trained using the Adam optimizer and evaluated on a validation set derived from an 80/20 training-validation split. The objective function maximizes the validation accuracy. Up to 50 candidate models were evaluated, with the best-performing configuration automatically stored.

This procedure resulted in a robust CNN architecture that demonstrated high validation accuracy. Importantly, the optimizer ensured that the selected model not only performed well on synthetic training data but also generalized effectively to

FIGURE 7. Optimization procedure - identifying the best combination of network metrics and training hyperparameters for highest validation accuracy

recorded pressure measurements from real compressor damage scenarios, synthetic damage scenarios including blade passing signatures different from the reference and even under signal noise. Variables of the best performing model are summarized

TABLE 2. Model network parameter and hyperparameter

Filter size	Block 1: 2^5 , Block 2: 4^5 , Block 3: 8^5
Nodes	Layer 1: 2^7 , Layer 2: $2^7/2$
Learning rate	$9.88 \cdot 10^{-5}$
L2 regularization	$3.22 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Dropout rate	29%
Mini batch size	46

FIGURE 8. Training and validation of multi-class model, trained on synthetic data - Accuracy 97.08%

in Table 2.

Training and Validation

The best-performing model identified through Bayesian optimization was saved for further analysis, and its training and validation process is in Figure 8. Remarkably, after only three epochs, the network was already able to distinguish between the different damage types, as reflected in the high training and validation accuracy as well as the corresponding loss curves. Throughout the training process, the training and validation metrics closely aligned, indicating that the model did not suffer from overfitting. After 20 epochs, the training was completed, and the final validation was conducted using the synthetic validation dataset. The results were evaluated with a confusion matrix, providing a detailed representation of classification accuracy across the different damage categories. All damage classes were predicted correctly by the model, as indicated by the con-

FIGURE 9. Experimentally obtained damage scenarios for the three selected damage types - unfiltered casing pressures

fusion matrix, where entries are exclusively located along the diagonal. This demonstrates that every predicted validation case corresponds exactly to its true class.

Model robustness - real damage scenarios

To further validate the model's robustness, an additional testing phase was conducted using experimental data instead of synthetically generated data. In this step, multiple damaged blades of the same type were installed in the test rig, with their positions randomly distributed over the rotor circumference. For this validation, multiple rotor configurations were tested, each containing a minimum of one and a maximum of five damaged blades of the same damage type. With four different distributions for each damage type and three pressure signals recorded, a total of 36 data sequences were generated out of which multiple segments having a length of a single rotor revolution have been randomly extracted.

Unlike the training phase with synthetic data, the validation was performed on raw, unprocessed pressure signals without phase-averaging (Figure 9). Model performance was again assessed through a confusion matrix (Figure 10), yielding an overall accuracy of 96.5%. The most frequent misclassifications occurred in the twist damage case with 86.1% being true positive. Nevertheless, a key outcome is that all damage scenarios were correctly identified as damage, with none misclassified as undamaged. This demonstrates that the model is both robust and

True Class	REF	800				100.0%	
	BO		800			100.0%	
	TW		111	689		86.1%	13.9%
	BE				800	100.0%	
		REF	BO	TW	BE		
		Predicted Class					

FIGURE 10. Validation of classifier using experimentally obtained damage scenarios, 96.5% accuracy

generalizable, confirming its applicability to real damage conditions. The model remained accurate in predicting damage types even when tested with data recorded at operating points different from DP and NS, which were used for training and validation. This suggests that damage anomalies dominate over blade signature amplitude variations, allowing the model to capture the most relevant features for classification effectively.

Model robustness - various blade passing signatures

In the next step, we aimed to demonstrate the model's generalizability by applying damage scenarios from an arbitrary compressor with variants of blade profile geometries resulting in new base line blade passing signatures. To this end, synthetic damage scenarios were generated by superimposing the previously extracted damage signatures onto blade passing signatures with varying amplitudes and harmonic asymmetries.

FIGURE 11. Artificial reference blade passing signatures; variation of asymmetry of harmonic wave and amplitudes

Figure 11 illustrates three exemplary blade passing signatures, one of which exhibits an increased amplitude.

$$s[n] = A \cdot \begin{cases} \cos\left(\frac{\pi k}{\lfloor T \cdot \alpha \rfloor}\right), & 0 \leq k < \lfloor T \cdot \alpha \rfloor, \\ \cos\left(\pi + \frac{\pi(k - \lfloor T \cdot \alpha \rfloor)}{T - \lfloor T \cdot \alpha \rfloor}\right), & \lfloor T \cdot \alpha \rfloor \leq k < T, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The new signature s was calculated using eqn. 4, where A is the amplitude, T the number of samples per period, α

True Class	REF	2400				100.0%	
	BO		2400			100.0%	
	TW	1	33	2366		98.6%	1.4%
	BE		251		2149	89.5%	10.5%
		REF	BO	TW	BE		
		Predicted Class					

FIGURE 12. Validation of classifier using synthetic damage scenarios based on artificial blade passing signatures, 97% accuracy

FIGURE 13. Model accuracy as a function of Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

the asymmetry factor (fraction of the rise phase) and k the intra-period sample index. Using these modified signals, new validation datasets were created for the three damage types and subsequently evaluated with the initially trained model.

The resulting confusion matrix in Figure 12 confirms that the model remains highly accurate, achieving a validation accuracy of 97% even when applied to blade passing signatures that deviate from those used for training. In this validation, most false classifications occurred for the bent blade case, while only one out of 7200 damage scenarios was incorrectly identified as undamaged. Even the newly introduced reference blade passing signatures without damage were correctly classified, further demonstrating the model's generalizability and its ability to focus specifically on damage-related anomalies. This outcome underlines the robustness and adaptability of the model across different compressor blade passing signatures.

Model robustness - signal noise

Another study was conducted to evaluate the robustness of the model against signal noise. For this purpose, noise with incrementally increasing amplitude was added to the validation data obtained from experimental damage scenarios, and the resulting signals were used as input for the trained model. As the noise amplitude increases, the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

decreases. Figure 13 illustrates the validation accuracy as a function of SNR. The model remained highly accurate from SNR=100dB (no noise) down to approximately 14dB. However, below 10dB, all damage cases were misclassified as undamaged, leading to an accuracy of only 25%. Despite this drop, the results demonstrate that the model is generally robust against signal noise.

5 COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

To validate the real-time performance of the CNN model, tests were conducted on a synthetic dataset simulating the sudden onset of blade damage. For each damage type, the continuous time-resolved pressure signal was segmented into sequences corresponding to single rotor revolutions and subsequently fed into the model. The model output was a class label indicating either the specific damage type or an undamaged rotor.

Figure 14 illustrates, for each damage scenario, the corresponding pressure signals with damage consistently introduced at 20.4 seconds, alongside the model-predicted labels. The compressor damage index (CDI) obtained from the cepstrum analysis is also shown for comparison. The results demonstrate that the CNN model detects specific damage types with the temporal resolution of a single rotor revolution. Once damage occurs, the predicted class consistently switches from “undamaged rotor” (REF) to the respective damage class (BE, TW, BO), without any instances of misclassifications. Similarly, the CDI exhibits a sharp amplitude increase at the onset of damage, clearly indicating the event. Quantitatively, the CDI percent change at onset was $\Delta\% = 92.35\%$ (BE), 56.89% (BO10), 80.28% (BO50)¹, and 70.51% (TW). Because the CDI is computed frame-wise from short-time spectra, a long FFT window (e.g., $N = 2^{15}$) integrates samples over a substantial time span. If the damage onset falls within that span, frames whose nominal timestamp precedes the event still contain post-onset samples, causing the aggregated cepstral energy (and thus the CDI) to rise before the true onset. The apparent lead reflects the finite time resolution and window centering/overlap of the estimator rather than a physical precursor.

Both methods can support protective shutdown after damage onset, but their capabilities differ. The real-cepstrum-based CDI detects the occurrence of damage but does not resolve damage class, whereas the CNN both detects and classifies with approximately one-revolution temporal resolution. The CDI incurs window-length latency due to FFT framing yet is simpler to deploy on existing data-acquisition/digital signal processing hardware. Being deterministic and physics-based, the CDI requires no labeled training data, has bounded compute and memory demand, and remains interpretable through aggregation of speed-synchronous cepstral energy relative to a healthy baseline.

FIGURE 14. CNN model and CDI applied to synthetic data simulating a sudden occurrence of damage

This transparency facilitates calibration and certification and reduces vulnerability to dataset shift compared with learned models. Neural-network approaches generally require greater computational resources and storage, constraining drop-in deployment.

¹This result is plotted in Fig. 14

FIGURE 15. Frequency analysis for each damage type, comparison to undamaged rotor (black)

We additionally performed frequency-domain analyses of the signals corresponding to the different damage scenarios. The resulting damage spectra, shown in Figure 15 (red), are compared against the spectrum of the undamaged rotor (black). For the undamaged case, the spectrum is characterized solely by the dominant BPF and its higher harmonics. In contrast, the introduction of damage gives rise to additional engine-order peaks alongside the BPF. Among the examined cases, the 50% breakout at multiple blades produces the most pronounced increases in engine-order amplitudes, whereas the bent blade scenario and small breakage result in only minor spectral changes. The introduced CDI Pipeline is well suited to detect and leverage these spectral changes using cepstral analysis.

6 DISCUSSION

This section discusses the implications of the study’s findings. Section 6.1 addresses the integration of cepstrum-based and

machine learning methods into a comprehensive damage detection strategy, while Section 6.2 considers their impact on maintenance practices and turbomachinery applications.

Integration of Methods

Combining the real-cepstrum-based Compressor Damage Index (CDI) with a convolutional neural network (CNN) uses the strengths of both approaches. The CDI offers a simple, transparent detector: it tracks speed-synchronous cepstral energy and signals when behavior departs from a healthy baseline. The CNN adds what the CDI does not provide - classification of the damage type - at a temporal resolution of roughly one rotor revolution. A possible practical workflow is tiered. The CDI runs continuously on streaming frames; if its value exceeds a calibrated threshold for M consecutive frames, the system calls the CNN on that time segment to assign a damage class. Time-stamping frames at their end reduces the apparent pre-onset rise caused by long FFT windows.

Fusion can be implemented in two straightforward ways. *Feature fusion* augments the CNN input with CDI-derived cepstral aggregates, which helps stabilize performance across operating conditions and can reduce the amount of training data needed. *Decision fusion* combines the CDI score with the CNN output using simple rules (e.g., require agreement or require persistence before escalation). If the CNN is uncertain or unavailable, the CDI alone maintains anomaly alarming; if only the CNN indicates damage, persistence over several frames is required.

This integration keeps baseline computation low, preserves an interpretable detection path for verification, and still delivers rapid alarms with specific fault labels to support maintenance decisions.

Implications for Turbomachinery Maintenance

A combined CDI–CNN scheme enables a shift from time-based preventive maintenance to condition-based interventions. The real-cepstrum-based CDI provides continuous, low-cost monitoring with bounded compute; threshold exceedance flags deviation from a healthy baseline, while the CNN supplies a damage class to guide inspection scope and parts provisioning.

For scheduling, early CDI deviations create lead time to align corrective actions with planned outages, reducing forced shutdowns and collateral damage. Class information narrows troubleshooting, shortens borescope and non-destructive testing activities, and focuses work on suspect stages or rows. Trending of baseline-normalized CDI and class persistence supports escalation rules; time-stamping frames at their end yields accurate event dating despite long FFT windows.

Economic impact arises from lower unplanned downtime, targeted inspections, and reduced false positives when CDI scores

and CNN posteriors are fused with persistence or agreement logic. For predictive maintenance, CDI trajectories and class probabilities can feed remaining-useful-life models and fleet-level risk scoring. Practical deployment requires per-unit baseline calibration, periodic drift checks, and data governance for rates, storage, and audit trails. The interpretable CDI metric supports verification and certification, and the CNN adds detail where compute resources permit, providing a scalable path to on-engine monitoring.

7 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Two complementary approaches for damage detection and classification in axial compressors based on time-resolved pressure measurements have been proposed. The first is a cepstrum-based method, which yields the compressor damage index (CDI) and provides a precise indication of the sudden occurrence of damage. The second is a deep learning-based approach employing a multiclass CNN, which not only detects damage but also identifies the specific blade damage type. Importantly, both approaches eliminate the need for visual inspection, offering significant advantages for predictive maintenance strategies.

Based on the recent findings and with a view toward practical applicability of the AI-based approach, several directions for future research are proposed. This study has primarily served as a proof of concept, demonstrating the potential of CNNs to identify specific damage types in compressors. However, it is clear that in real-world applications no customer would install pressure sensors above each rotor of a multistage axial compressor. A more feasible path forward is the use of existing instrumentation capable of capturing equivalent or comparable data to that used in this study.

One promising option is the deployment of piezoelectric sensors downstream of the compressor, or at least downstream of the investigated stage. Such instrumentation is already standard in stationary gas turbines, where it is employed to detect burner resonances. A logical follow-up study would therefore involve placing a microphone downstream of the experimental compressor stage and applying the same data management and augmentation strategies for training and validating the neural network. At the same time, the scope of damage scenarios should be expanded to include conditions such as missing blades or mis-staggering of variable stator vanes (VSVs).

Finally, considering the challenges associated with model storage and deployment, network development should incorporate an additional optimization objective: minimizing the required architecture size while retaining robust classification performance. This step would enhance the practicality of AI-based methods for real-time implementation in industrial compressor systems.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors wish to extend their gratitude to Siemens Energy Global GmbH & Co. KG for their general support, which has significantly contributed to the success of this work. We also acknowledge the Stiftung Innovation in der Hochschullehre for their generous funding of the CATAO test rig, enabling key advances in our research. This support has been essential in driving forward the innovations presented in this publication.

Data Availability

The failure-signature datasets used in this study are publicly available at [doi:10.5281/zenodo.17206489](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17206489).

REFERENCES

- [1] Pfeifer, U., and Brummel, H.-G., 2015. Apparatus and method for detecting the current damaged state of a machine. WO Patent App. PCT/EP2014/073098. Patent No. WO 2015/090698 A1, published June 25, 2015.
- [2] Mathioudakis, K., Papathanasiou, A., Loukis, E., and Papailiou, K., 1991. "Fast Response Wall Pressure Measurement as a Means of Gas Turbine Blade Fault Identification". *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **113**(2), 04, pp. 269–275.
- [3] Loukis, E., Mathioudakis, K., and Papailiou, K., 1992. "A Procedure for Automated Gas Turbine Blade Fault Identification Based on Spectral Pattern Analysis". *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **114**(2), 04, pp. 201–208.
- [4] Loukis, E., Wetta, P., Mathioudakis, K., Papathanasiou, A., and Papailiou, K., 1991. "Combination of Different Unsteady Quantity Measurements for Gas Turbine Blade Fault Diagnosis". In Volume 5: Manufacturing Materials and Metallurgy; Ceramics; Structures and Dynamics; Controls, Diagnostics and Instrumentation; General, Turbo Expo: Power for Land, Sea, and Air, p. V005T15A004.
- [5] Taylor, J. V., Conduit, B., Dickens, A., Hall, C., Hillel, M., and Miller, R. J., 2020. "Predicting the Operability of Damaged Compressors Using Machine Learning". *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **142**(5), 04, p. 051010.
- [6] Aust, J., and Pons, D., 2021. "Methodology for evaluating risk of visual inspection tasks of aircraft engine blades". *Aerospace*, **8**(4).
- [7] Aust, J., and Pons, D., 2019. "Taxonomy of gas turbine blade defects". *Aerospace*, **6**(5).
- [8] Randall, R. B., 2010. *Vibration-based Condition Monitoring - Industrial, Aerospace, and Automotive Applications*. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.
- [9] Norton, M. P., and Karczub, D. G., 2003. *Fundamentals of Noise and Vibration Analysis for Engineers*, 2nd edition ed. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.